

Ethical Issues in Research Writing

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ABSTRACT

This paper is based on the ethics of research writing. Plagiarism means stealing of ideas or thoughts or concepts of other person as your own without quoting or citing or referencing them. Representing other person thought as your own original work is an offence, so in order to avoid such plagiarism a author should know which are the common forms of plagiarism, what is the consequences of plagiarism, how to avoid them and what are the tools available to check plagiarism.

KEYWORD: *Ethics, research writing, plagiarism, etc.*

INTRODUCTION

Ethics govern every facet in human life. Even in academics ethical norms are set to avoid plagiarism. Plagiarism is a stealing of ideas, concepts or words of others as yours own without citing or quoting or referencing them intentionally or unintentionally. It is one form of cheating and if you caught then it will commit as an academic offense.

Meaning of Plagiarism:

Plagiarism is the wrongful appropriation, stealing and publication of another author's language, thought, ideas, concepts or expression and representation of them as your own original work.

According to BelaGipp, "Academic Plagiarism encompasses the use of ideas, concepts, words or structure without appropriately acknowledging the source to benefit in a setting where originality is expected."

According to Standford, "Plagiarism is the use, without giving reasonable and appropriate credit to or acknowledging the author or source, of author

person's original work, whether such work is made up of code, formula, ideas, language, research, strategies, writing or other form."

Characteristics of Plagiarism:

- Plagiarism is considered as academic dishonesty.
- It is not defined or published or punished by law, but rather by institutions including professional In academia and industry, it is a serious ethical offense.
- Plagiarism associations, educational institutions, and commercial entities, such as publishing companies.

Common Forms of Plagiarism:

1. Representing someone else work as your own work.
2. Re-writing their own previous research paper material without giving citation in present work.
3. Copying others work without properly citing the actual source.
4. Interweaving various source materials without properly citing the original source.
5. Writing research paper or essay or students assignment by melding together the cited part and uncited part.
6. Relying too much on others works fails to bring their original ideas into their own work.

Types of Plagiarism:

➤ Direct Plagiarism:

Most probably this type of plagiarism happen with the students and researchers, they usually copy the exact piece of someone else work as their own work without giving credit to the original author. Usually in this cases if the original source is published in any journal article or book chapter, in this circumstances plagiarism cannot be avoided

by paraphrasing the primary source or acknowledging its use into footnote. Note that it is an academic crime to plagiarize deliberately that can result in serious punishment.

➤ **Self-Plagiarism:**

Self-Plagiarism is that when author republishes their own previous written work as their present work and that is without citing them or quoting them, whatever the copied material it may be either the entire part or partial part of previous work must be quote. It is one kind of submitting multiple copies of the previous research paper or duplication of it.

➤ **Mosaic Plagiarism:**

Mosaic Plagiarism represents stealing the ideas or words from other source and without giving them quotation marks and putting it into your own paper. In other words writing authors concepts by using synonyms words but preserving the actual structure and meaning of the original document. Even though the source is mention in the footnote. This type of plagiarism leads to crime and punishable.

➤ **Accidental Plagiarism:**

Accidental Plagiarism occurs when the researcher or a student or those who writing the paper ignores citing the original source as well as makes improper paraphrasing. As compare to other form of plagiarism accidental plagiarism is taken seriously.

➤ **Patchwork Plagiarism:**

This type of plagiarism happens in many cases where a student or researcher steals the ideas, phrase, sentences and paragraphs from different sources and putting them together into essays. In this situation it is very difficult to assess.

Consequences of Plagiarism:

Due to the rapid development in the field of technology, if anyone tries to copy others ideas or concepts he / she can be caught within no time with the help of plagiarism detection software. The consequences of plagiarism can be personal, professional, ethical or legal. Plagiarist may include journalists, authors, academics, students, professionals and others. Consequences of plagiarism includes as follows:

➤ **Destroyed Students Reputation:**

In schools, colleges and universities plagiarism takes very seriously. If a student caught with plagiarism it can directly cause a student to be

suspended or expelled from the institution, their academic record can reflect the ethics, possibly causing the student to be barred from entering college from high school to or another college. Sometime school suspend a student for their first violation.

➤ **Destroyed Professional Reputation:**

If a professionals like business person, politician or any other person find with plagiarism will cause damage to their entire career. Not only her/she will fired or led down from their current position but they will find difficulty to obtain another job.

Actions to be taken against Plagiarism:

- Within academic institution if duplication is done by students, professors or researchers it is considered as academic dishonesty or academic fraud.
- Journalism plagiarism is considered as a breach of journalistic ethics and reporters caught in plagiarizing typically face disciplinary measures ranging from suspension to termination from service.
- For students plagiarising is considered to be a serious offence that can be turn into punishment such as giving failing grade or particular assignment or for the entire course or even terminates from institution.
- For researcher and professors plagiarism leads to punishable under sanctions ranging from suspension or termination, along with the loss of credibility and perceived integrity.

Ways to avoid Plagiarism:

1. Paraphrasing:

While doing your research if you found any information which is perfect for your research paper / thesis / dissertation, make sure that you will not copy the same words which is their in the original paper. Read it and put it into your own words. Make sure that you do not copy verbatim more than two words in a row from the text you have found. If you do use more than two words together, you will have to use quotation marks.

2. Cite:

Citing the copied material is the best way to avoid plagiarism. For this you can follow any document formatting guideline which is being followed by your educational institution or the institution that issued the research request (Eg. APA, ALA, Chicago, MLA, etc). This citing style usually

includes details like addition of author name, title of the research paper, publication, date of publication, etc. Improper citing which leads to plagiarism.

3. Quotation:

Use quotation marks for those parts which you are going to use from other author. While quoting any source use an exact quoting format the way it appears.

4. Citing Quotes:

Here citing a quote which is different from citing paraphrased materials which is usually follow the practice of using page numbers or a paragraph number in the case of web content.

5. Referencing:

Using references is one of the most effective ways to avoid plagiarism by including reference pages at the end of your research paper. At the same time this reference pages should have to meet the document formatting guideline which is being used by your institution, In this case the information is accurate and it provides details like author(s), date of publication, title and source. This will follow the direction for the source pages carefully.

Research:

- When writing an assignment it begin with collection of research notes, whether it may be the combination of concepts / ideas / words from other source and the students own ideas. Here you keep notes on index cards, in a loose-leaf binding, or an old envelope in a desk drawer, it is important to record and organise them in such a way that vital information is not lost.
- Maintain perfect and complete track of sources usually copy of authors, title and addition information about the source publication number of pages from which notes or quotes were taken.
- Carefully distinguish between your own ideas and others ideas even if you use other conclusion acknowledge them first.
- Carefully distinguish between your own concept and those of others. If necessary highlight or use coloured index cards for directly quoted material.

Writing:

When you start your writing carrier put yours ideas together in a written form and consider the following things:

- Start your writing in an original manner. Never go for copying others thought or concept in your

writing. Remember that it is your ideas, yours unique contribution to your writing and not the attempt of summarizing or paraphrasing of others work.

- As if you are using others ideas / concepts in your work give them quotation marks. Do not mess with paraphrasing.
- After completion of your work read it first and draft carefully. See the difference between your copied material and the original source, give them quotes or paraphrase them. And finally see is there enough of your own contribution in your paper or not?

Editing:

After completion of your writing, consider what you have drawn from another source and ask yourself the following:

- Is the ideas / concepts expressed in the paper is entirely my own? Whatever the general language I used / choice of word is my own?
- Here, if both the questions answer is "NO" then credit should be given to the original author and if only second question answer is "NO" then whatever material you have drawn from another work either you quote them directly or rewrite in your own words.

List of free source Plagiarism detection Software:

- Dupli Checker
- Paperrater
- Plagiarism Checker
- Plagium
- Quetext
- Viper
- Small SEO Tools
- Plagiarism Check
- Dust ball
- Desktop Plagiarism Checker
- Copy Tracker

Paid Plagiarism Detector Software:

- Plagiarism Checker X
- Plagiarism Detector
- Plagiarism Finder Pro
- Anti Plagiarism.NET

Conclusion:

Plagiarism is the stealing of others ideas or concepts or words and representing them as yours own work. Avoiding plagiarism is very important. And therefore the punishment should be applying on the person

those who copy the other work without citing / quoting / referencing them. Hence it is very important for students to understand what is plagiarism and the consequences of plagiarising others ideas.

Bibliography

1. (n.d.). Retrieved 03 06, 2018, from <https://prime-essay.net/common-types-of-plagiarism>
2. (n.d.). Retrieved from <http://en.writecheck.com/ways-to-avoid-plagiarism>
3. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://elearningindustry.com/top-10-free-plagiarism-detection-tools-for-teachers>
4. (n.d.). Retrieved from <http://www.ithenticate.com/resorces/6-conequences-of-plagiarism>
5. Rani, S. (2018). Ethical issues in research, writing and publication. *International Journal of Research*, 1771-1774.

